
Creation of Casual Fashion Design with the Source Idea of *Jaranan Buto*

Ailsa Damayanti¹, Deny Arifiana², Mein Kharnolis³, Inty Nahari⁴

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia¹

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia²

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia³

Fashion Education Study Program, Faculty of Engineering, State University of Surabaya, Indonesia⁴

Corresponding Email: ailsa.20069@mhs.unesa.ac.id*

Abstract

Jaranan Jaranan Buto folk dance originates from Banyuwangi and refers to the story of Palawan Minakjinggo in the battle against Kebo Mawet. This art is created from the mixture of osing culture with Mataraman kingdom. Casual fashion is clothing that is simple, practical, comfortable to wear, and has a loose size and is used in everyday life. Jaranan Buto's clothing has a similar shape to casual clothing. To further introduce the culture of the Osing tribe, this Jaranan Buto fashion will be developed into a casual fashion that is comfortable for daily use. The purpose of this research is to describe the creation process and the finished result of the creation of a casual fashion design with the source idea of Jaranan Buto. This research method uses the creation method, which has 3 stages, namely exploration, design, and realization. The results of this research are (1) the process of creating a casual fashion design with the idea source of Jaranan Buto, (2) the results of creating 3 casual outfits with the idea source of Jaranan Buto, consisting of 2 casual female outfits and 1 casual male outfit. 2 casual outfits consisted of 2 parts, namely tops and pants, while 1 casual outfit consisted of 3 parts, namely tops, pants, and obi.

Keywords: Casual Wear, Jaranan Buto, Banyuwangi

Abstrak

Tarian rakyat Jaranan Jaranan Buto berasal dari Banyuwangi yang mengacu pada kisah Palawan Minakjinggo dalam pertempuran melawan kebo mawet. Kesenian ini tercipta dari percampuran budaya osing dengan kerajaan Mataraman. Busana casual adalah busana yang simple, praktis, nyaman dipakai, serta mempunyai ukuran longgar dan digunakan kehidupan sehari – hari. Busana Jaranan Buto memiliki kemiripan bentuk dengan busana casual. Untuk lebih mengenalkan budaya suku osing, busana Jaranan Buto ini akan dikembangkan menjadi

busana casual yang nyam digunakan sehari – hari. Tujuan penelitian ini untuk mendeskripsikan proses penciptaan dan hasil jadi desain busana casual dengan sumber ide Jaranan Buto. Metode penelitian ini menggunakan metode penciptaan karya yang memiliki 4 tahapan , yaitu pra perancangan, perancangan, perwujudan, dan diseminasi karya. Hasil penelitian ini berupa (1) proses penciptaan busana casual dengan sumber ide jaranan buto , (2) Hasil penciptaan 3 busana casual dengan sumber ide jaranan buto, yang terdiri dari 2 busana casual Wanita dan 1 busana casual pria. 2 busana casual berupa 2 bagian yaitu atasan dan celana sedangkan 1 busana casual terdiri dari 3 bagian, yaitu atasan, celana, dan obi.

Kata kunci: *Desain Busana Santai, Jaranan Buto, Banyuwangi*

Introduction

Indonesia is a country rich in diversity from Sabang to Merauke. Indonesia's wealth lies not only in its natural resources, but also in its cultural diversity. Culture is the pattern of life of a group of people that is systematically passed down from generation to generation through the learning process to create a way of life that suits the environment (Wibowo, 2013: 15-16). Culture in Indonesia is created systematically from generation to generation so that art is created. Art is a basic human need wherever it is, in various situations and conditions.

Art in Indonesia has a significant role in the fashion industry, fashion plays an important role in appearance, style, and trends in the lives of Indonesian people. The rapid development of fashion in Indonesia has had a huge impact on society, which not only follows trends but also makes daily lifestyle an important thing. This shows that looking fashionable and stylish in accordance with fashion developments has become a very relevant thing for Indonesians. The fashion industry in Indonesia has also experienced significant development with the influence of cultural elements from within and outside the country.

The fashion industry often holds fashion shows to introduce designers' works to the public. As an example of the dissemination of this work, Gelar Kreasi Busana Unesa 2024 is a fashion show that attracts attention. The big theme of the event was JAGAD OSING, which was inspired by the rich culture that developed in the osing area, East Java. The fashion displayed took elements of osing culture in the form of folk dance, Jaranan Buto.

Jaranan Buto folk dance originates from Banyuwangi which is spread almost throughout the countryside. The idea of creating this dance refers to the story of the hero Minakjingga in the fight against Kebo Mawet (Hidayah and Suharti, 2023: 2). This art originated in Banyuwangi, created from the cultural mixing of the Osing tribe with the Mataraman kingdom. Jaranan Buto is a depiction of the figure of “Buto” who has a mighty and creepy face that describes the figure of King Minak Jinggo. “Buto” is an image of a big-headed person who is arrogant, while piggybank means that the character should not imitate something bad and only good things should be imitated or scorned. Raja Minak Jinggo is also accompanied by “Jaran” or a replica of a horse commonly called a braid. Jaranan buto has the philosophy of the spirit of struggle, chivalry and hard work. The whip carried by the character “Buto” is one of the Jaranan Buto heirlooms. The theme to be displayed is the value of struggle and heroism.

Jaranan Buto dance has several important elements in its performance structure. the makeup and costume work used in this dance depicts the figure of Duke Minakjingga who is large and dashing (Hidayah and Suharti, 2023: 2). The depiction of Jaranan Buto's costume and silhouette inspired the creation of a casual outfit with an edgy style.

Makeup work is the art of changing the appearance of the face to be more perfect than before (Sabri, et al, 2016: 2). Jaranan Buto's makeup uses canines, dreadlocks, red, white, black, and powder. Jaranan Buto has 3 characters of makeup work, namely Buto Prenges, Buto Teleng, and Buto Gantengan (Kusuma, 2019). Generally, dancers use makeup with a red base color combined with black and white colours to give a bold impression. This combination also shows the cruel, frightening, and greedy nature of the giant character.

Clothing is everything that is worn by humans, both men and women, from head to toe on certain occasions (Paramita, et al : 2019). The function of clothing is to protect the body and cover the shortcomings and advantages of the body. Clothing is also plays role in social life which functions as a tool to express the role of everyone who wears it (Sahis, 2014 : 103). Clothing is also divided several occasions, one of which is casual wear.

Casual fashion is clothing that is simple, practical, comfortable to wear, and has a loose size and is used daily (Akmal and Prihatin, 2020:1 – 6). Casual fashion is very popular with all people from various circle. Jaranan Buto fashion has similarities with everyday casual fashion. The shape of the clothes is loose at the top and bottom of the clothes so that it is comfortable to move. Because of the similarity in the form of Jaranan Buto clothing, the author is interested in creating casual clothing with the source of Jaranan Buto dance ideas that can attract public interest in preserving the arts in Indonesia.

This research aims to describe the process of creation and finished result of the creation of leisurewear design with the source idea of Jaranan Buto. In addition, this research is expected to make a significant contribution to the preservation and development of traditional arts in Banyuwangi, be able to add insight into Banyuwangi culture and the creation of leisurewear with a source of regional art ideas so as to create better works of art.

Research Method

This research method is based on the creation method, which is a research approach that focuses on creating new works through research and practice. According to Hendriyana (2022), the process of creating artwork involves several stages that must be passed.

Figure 1 Flow of Work Creation
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Pre-Design

The source of ideas is a flash of creative ideas that arise spontaneously or through the process of observation in a certain location and time or in a new environment and atmosphere. The idea or concept in leisure wear design is Jaranan Buto. The main color used is red and black combined with yellow to create an edgy and luxurious impression in accordance with the source of the idea (Figure 2) The following moodboard is the result of exploring the idea of Jaranan Buto Dance:

Figure 2 Moodboard Jaranan Buto
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Design

Fashion design is a visual representation of the concept of clothing illustrated through images by taking into account design principles that can be understood by others, so that it can be realized in the form of clothing as a result of the planning that has been compiled (Susiana & Wening, 2015). Here are some of the stages of designing this work:

1. Alternative Design

Alternative design in fashion refers to different innovative concepts in the creation of clothing or accessories, such as material selection, cut style, color, and decorative details, which are different from traditional designs.

a. Alternative Sketch

Alternative sketches are the first step in making artwork, where the author makes several design sketches. Here are some alternative fashion designs that will later be chosen to be realized. Here are the alternative sketches of women's casual wear:

Figure 3 Alternative Design Female
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Here's an alternative sketch of men's casual wear:

Figure 4 Alternative Design Male
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

b. Color sketches

At this stage, after the sketch design is perfected, the author gives warrants according

to the colorplan found on the moodboard. The following is a color sketch of women's casual wear:

Figure 5 Colour Sketches Female
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Here's a colored sketch of men's casual wear:

Figure 6 Colour Sketches Male
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

2. Selected Design

The selected design is the result of a selection that considers the desired criteria. This design was made based on the existing concept. The selected designs were chosen through discussion, assessment, and consideration by three experts in the field of design and fashion. Furthermore, the selected designs will be realized in the form of two casual outfits for women and one casual outfit for men. Here are the selected designs for women's and men's clothing:

Figure 7 Selected Design
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

3. Working Drawing

Working drawings are detailed descriptions of designs that will serve as guidelines for realizing concepts into physical works of art. Working drawings help in reading design details to minimize errors during the fashion making process. Working drawings include production design 1 and production design 2. The following are working drawings of the selected fashion designs::

a. Fashion No. 25 and 26

Figure 8 Working Drawing Fashion No. 25 and 26
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Production design one explains that garments No 25 and 26 have several parts. The bulging sleeve shape is characteristic of the silhouette of the jaranan buto. There are many pieces and stacked in the pants. Meanwhile, Production Design two explains the size of the parts of the outfit which aims to facilitate the realization of the work. The size of the clothing parts is adjusted to the model's body size, namely collar 12 cm, sleeves 57 cm, tassel length 14 cm, zipper length 37 cm, cut width 3 - 7 cm.

b. Fashion No 11 and 12

Figure 9 Working Design Fashion No. 11 and 12
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Production design one explains that garments No 11 and 12 have several parts. The bulging sleeve shape is characteristic of the silhouette of the jaranan buto. While Production Design two explains the size of the parts of the outfit which aims to facilitate the realization of the work. The size of the clothing parts is adjusted to the model's bodysize, namely collar 12 cm, sleeve 57 cm, tassel length 14 cm, zipper length 65 cm, cut width 3 - 7 cm..

c. Fashion No 27 and 28

Figure 10 Working Design Fashion No. 27 and 28
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Production design one explains that dresses No 27 and 28 have several parts. Stacked and oversized clothing is characteristic of jaranan buto. Equipped with tassel pieces on the pants and the body looks plain. Meanwhile, Production Design two explains the size of the parts of the outfit which aims to facilitate the realization of the work. The size of the clothing parts is adjusted to the model's body size, namely collar 12 cm, sleeves 57 cm, tassel length 14 cm, zipper length 50 cm, cut width 3 - 7 cm.

4. Model/Master/Prototype

Prototype is an initial description of a product that will be made. This is done to determine the suitability between the design and the product to be made, so that it can be corrected if an error occurs. Here are the prototypes of men's and women's casual wear:

Figure 11 Fashion Prototype
(Doc : Damayanti, 2024)

Fashion Pattern Rupture Making

Figure 15 Fashion Pattern Rupture Making No. 11 and 12
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

c. Fashion No 27 and 28

Basic Fashion Pattern Making

Figure 16 Basic Pattern Making No. 27 and 28
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Fashion Pattern Rupture Making

Figure 17 Fashion Pattern Rupture Making No. 27 and 28
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

2. Stages of Fashion Sewing

The following are the stages of sewing clothes, (1) Drawing fashion patterns such as designs and design sizes, (2) Preparing tools and materials, (3) Cutting the main material according to the pattern, (4) Cutting the furing material according to the pattern, (5) Sewing the parts of the outfit according to the design, (6) Installing zippers and waistbands according to the outfit, (7) Performing the completion stage of the outfit.

3. Stages of Making Teksmo

The following are the stages of making textmo in this creation, (1) Prepare tools and materials, (2) Draw the textmo design, (3) Embroider the design that has been

prepared, (4) make knits to display a 3d impression on the textmo made, (5) sew knits on the embroidery that has been made, (6) do the final finishing.

Dissemination of Work

1. Type Of Publication Selected

The type of publication to display the work is the fashion show Jagad Osing 35th Annual Fashion Show held at the Gazebo in front of the rectorate of unesa tongue on June 2, 2024. The event was also attended by unesa lecturers, experts in fashion, and invited guests (family).

Figure 18 Gazebo Unesa Lidah Wetan
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

Publications were also carried out through AFS Unesa Youtube Streaming and the official Instagram from Unesa. It is hoped that by choosing social media publications can reachout to the outside community to come to attend the show.

Figure 19 Youtube AFS Unesa

Figure 20 Instagram Resmi Unesa
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

2. Concept Of Presentation

The performance concept features a tron video about the origin of Jaranan Buto. The videodepicts the hero Adipati Minakjinggo fighting Kebo Mawet. Followed by a live Jaranan Buto dance performance accompanied by gamelan music and smoke reliefsthat depict the atmosphereof the war. This aims to provide an overview of the work regarding the inspiration for making the work

Results and Discussion

The results of making this work have several indicators, namely:

1. Type Of Work

The type of work made in this research is casual clothing inspired by Jaranan Buto.

2. Size

The size of this casual wear is adjusted to the size of the model.

3. Shape Structure

This casual fashion is inspired by Buto in Jaranan Buto dance. This fashion has a large and stacked shape. Equipped with tassels and many pieces in the outfit that illustrate the costume of Jaranan Buto. The main material used is cotton fabric combined with crinoline to display the stylized shape of the buto silhouette.

4. Meaning

Jaranan Buto has many components that can be used as a source of inspiration for this outfit. Buto has the meaning of a majestic, gallant, and strong character displaying a brave hero. In terms of color, black means wise, virtuous, and responsible. The red color has a brave meaning and the yellow color describes luxury and can also be used to describe the attributes of a king.

Figure 21 Results Of Casual Fashion
(Doc: Damayanti, 2024)

The results of the assessment of the work carried out by teaching practitioners based on the foundation of creation, state that:

1. Concept and Shape Aspect

Based on the concept and form aspects, the practitioner stated that the work was very good and in accordance with the function of the moodboard.

2. Aspects Of Idea Quality and Originally

The aspects of idea quality and originality are good and have been modified according to the source of the idea.

3. Ekspression Aspect

The expression aspect is considered good in expressing the work that has been made.

4. Comfort Aspect

The comfort aspect is considered good because the clothes are made loose and as comfortable as possible and use high quality materials.

5. Shape and Form of Work

The shape and form aspect of the work is considered good because it can realize the work in accordance with the source of ideas.

There are several indicators of assessment of the validity of casual fashion products. The following are indicators of casual fashion assessment criteria to determine the quality of the products produced:

1. Shape

The shape of the clothes is in accordance with the initial design, which has a bulging shape on the sleeves and has many cuts and tassels on the clothes.

2. Size

The size comparison between the product and the design is appropriate, namely with the size of the models.

3. Neatness

The neatness of this outfit is neat enough and suitable for use.

4. Colour

The colors in this outfit are black, red, and yellow. Which has the meaning of a wise and brave hero.

5. Consistency

The outfit is composed of 2 pieces and 3 pieces, in the form of tops and bottoms and edgy obi. On the top there is 3D buto embroidery and tassels that make the outfit look beautiful.

6. Final Result

The final result of the casual outfit with Jaranan Buto as the source of idea was in accordance with the initial design. The source of idea, concept, color, and shape are worth to be published. The fabric used in this outfit is cotton with a combination of crinoline to make the outfit look dashing.

Conclusion

The process of making this outfit went through several stages. The process of making this outfit went through several stages. The author chose Jaranan Buto Dance as the source of idea for making casual wear. Jaranan Buto dance was created from the combination of Osing culture with the Mataraman Kingdom. Jaranan Buto is a depiction of the figure of Minakjinggo who is mighty and has a knightly nature. This dance has several deep meanings, one of which is that as humans we can always manage worldly desires wisely. In accordance with the depiction of the figure of Minakjinggo, the form of clothing is made oversized and is intended for ages 20-25 years. The choice of 20-25 years old aims to attract the younger generation to preserve the culture of the Osing Tribe. The second stage is the design stage. This stage involves the process of making design sketches and colored designs which will later be selected by the supervisor to be realized. The third stage is the realization stage. At this stage the selected design will be realized into a product by making a fashion pattern first and then the process of sewing clothes and making to see if the clothes used are appropriate, if it is appropriate the sewing process is carried out until the product is finished and the fourth stage, namely the publication of the work in the form of a fashion show held at the Unesa tongue gazebo. and publication through Unesa's official Instagram and YouTube social media.

Results So casual clothing with the source idea of Jaranan Buto is composed of 2 pieces and 3 pieces, in the form of tops and bottoms and edgy-style obi. On the top there is 3D Buto embroidery and tassels. The final result of casual wear with the source of idea Jaranan Buto was in accordance with the initial design. The source of idea, concept, color, and shape are worth to be published. The material used in this outfit is cotton with a combination of crinoline to make the outfit look dashing.

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